

WHITE PAPER

I/O and Storage

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Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

Exascale represents a major leap in the evolution of supercomputing, not just another step after Terascale and Petascale. From a storage perspective, it marks a significant shift in system architecture. The immense compute power of Exascale introduces new challenges that render some current technologies insufficient, as they won't scale effectively. This calls for exploring new approaches to interfacing storage systems with supercomputers. At the same time, existing technologies must adapt and evolve to meet the demands of the Exascale era.

Some upcoming challenges in HPC may appear to be familiar but take on new forms. System scalability remains a key issue, but now must be considered alongside data scalability, especially with the rise of AI frameworks that place increased pressure on storage systems from both data and metadata perspectives. The evolution of compute hardware, particularly the widespread adoption of GPUs, has significantly impacted HPC, forcing a reconsideration of several paradigms, many of which are tied to storage systems. Storage hardware is also evolving, with broader adoption of SSDs and the introduction of ultra-fast NVMe buses. The storage hierarchy is shifting from the traditional two-tier model of tapes and rotating disks to a deeper, more complex structure with three or four levels. This new landscape complicates data placement, as data becomes increasingly heterogeneous, and previously unsolvable problems are now addressable in the Exascale era.

The first essential software component is middleware. Beyond scalability, energy efficiency, and performance, the increased complexity demands a focus on standardization, interoperability, resilience, fault tolerance, and security. As data scales to tens of exabytes and metadata to hundreds of

terabytes, minimizing data movement becomes crucial. This, however, contrasts with emerging paradigms like deeper storage hierarchies and disaggregated storage, requiring optimization of long-distance data transfers and placement of applications close to storage. Another strategy is reducing the amount of data transferred, for example, through computational storage, where some processing occurs directly on storage systems. Both these approaches partially address the full workflow requirements of large-scale scientific applications, moving beyond simply a single large application running on a single system. The sheer growth of data challenges traditional file systems, which struggle to scale sufficiently. Object stores offer an efficient alternative but introduce their own issues, particularly around interoperability and security. Heavily utilized in cloud systems, object stores foster a partial convergence between HPC and cloud computing. These exascale-driven advancements necessitate the introduction of new Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), shifting the focus beyond pure performance metrics. Energy consumption, in particular, becomes a critical factor, given the immense scale of all exascale systems, as do more varied I/O patterns.

Glossary of Acronyms

ADIOS – Adaptable IO System	ML – Machine Learning
AI – Artificial Intelligence	MPI-IO – Message Passing Interface I/O
API – Application Programming Interface	MSA – Modular Supercomputing Architecture
ASDF – Advanced Scientific Data Format	NetCDF – Network Common Data Form
CLI – Command-line Interface	NFS – Network File System
CPU – Central Processing Unit	NUMA – Non-Uniform Memory Access
DASI – Data Access and Storage Interface	NVM – Non-Volatile Memory
DAOS – Distributed Asynchronous Object Storage	NVMe – NVMe Express
DDoS – Distributed Denial-of-Service Attack	NVRAM – Non-Volatile RAM
DNA – Deoxyribonucleic Acid	PAM – Privileged Access Management
DOI – Digital Object Identifier	PCI – Peripheral Component Interconnect
DPU – Data Processing Unit	PFS – Parallel File System
DRAM – Dynamic RAM	PID – Process Identifier
EB – Exabyte	PnetCDF – Parallel NetCDF
FAIR – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse	POSIX – Portable Operating System Interface
FIDO2 – Fast IDentity Online 2	RADOS – Reliable Autonomic Distributed Object Store
FITS – Flexible Image Transport System	RAM – Random-Access Memory
FPGA – Field-Programmable Gate Array	RDM – Research Data Management
GB – Gigabyte	RDMA – Remote Direct Memory Access
GÉANT – Gigabit European Academic Network	RFP – Request for Proposal
GPU – Graphics Processing Unit	S3 – Simple Storage Service
GUI – Graphical User Interface	SAML – Security Assertion Markup Language
HBM – High Bandwidth Memory	SAS – Serial Attached SCSI
HCI – Hyperconverged Infrastructure	SATA – Serial AT Attachment
HDD – Hard Disk Drive	SCP – Secure Copy Protocol
HDF5 – Hierarchical Data Format 5	SCSI – Small Computer System Interface
HPC – High Performance Computing	SFTP – Secure File Transfer Protocol
HSM – Hierarchical Storage Management	SIMPL – Synchronous Interprocess Messaging Project for LINUX
HTTP – HyperText Transfer Protocol	SSD – Solid-State Drive
I/O – Input/Output	SSH – Secure Shell
IoT – Internet of Things	SSO – Single Sign-On
iRODS – integrated Rule-Oriented Data management System	STDIO – Standard I/O
KPI – Key Performance Indicator	T10-DIF – T10 Data Integrity Field
LAN – Local Area Network	T10-PI – T10 Protection Information
LDAP – Lightweight Directory Access Protocol	TB – Terabyte
MAN – Metropolitan Area Network	TCO – Total Cost of Ownership
MCSE – Memory-centric Storage for Exascale	TCP – Transmission Control Protocol
	UDP – User Datagram Protocol

Introduction

High-performance computing (HPC) systems, including supercomputers, are designed to handle complex, large-scale simulations across various domains, from high-energy physics experiments to artificial intelligence and digital twin modelling. One of the core challenges in these systems is not only executing computations efficiently, but also managing the massive volumes of data generated in the process. As HPC workloads grow in complexity, both computational power and storage architecture must scale to meet the increasing demand for processing and managing this data.

Storage systems serve as the critical backbone of HPC, responsible for storing the vast datasets produced by computations. These systems must provide not only sufficient capacity but also high bandwidth for rapid data transfer and fast metadata access. Balancing computational speed with data access performance is essential for maximizing the overall productivity of the system. As computing capacity increases, so does the demand for storage solutions capable of matching the growing need for throughput and speed of access.

A key challenge that arises is maintaining the ratio between storage access bandwidth and data volume. As both compute and storage systems evolve, ensuring that data can be accessed and transferred quickly becomes as critical as the computational power itself. Technologies like solid-state drives (SSDs) are increasingly favoured for their higher I/O bandwidth, but this requirement extends to all types of storage media. The relationship between computing power, storage capacity, and I/O performance now drives many architectural decisions in modern HPC systems,

where data must not only be abundant but also rapidly accessible. This dynamic necessitates a holistic approach to HPC architecture, with careful management of the interplay between computing and storage to optimize overall system performance.

In earlier generations of HPC, particularly during the terascale and petascale eras, I/O subsystems were often overprovisioned, offering more bandwidth and quality of service than most compute systems could fully utilize. This led to periods of underutilization, where storage systems remained idle much of the time. Storage procurement was typically based on peak performance estimates, which did not always reflect realistic usage patterns, frequently resulting in storage systems that were over-dimensioned relative to actual application needs.

The shift to exascale computing, however, has fundamentally altered this balance. The sheer complexity and scale of exascale supercomputers have placed unprecedented pressure on I/O subsystems, pushing them beyond their traditional capabilities. These systems now face demands that far exceed those of previous generations, especially when managing the large bursts of data generated by the growing memory footprints of exascale machines. As a result, I/O architectures must be reimaged, with new paradigms emerging to more efficiently balance performance, bandwidth, and capacity in order to meet the increasingly diverse requirements of modern HPC applications. This trend was already visible in previous editions of the Strategic Research Agenda, as shown in Figure 1, and is intensified by the advent of the exascale era.

SRA5 (2022)	SRA4 (2020)	SRA3 (2017)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Convergence of HPC and Cloud infrastructures ● Distributed Data Management ● Storage Infrastructure Co-Design with DPUs, FPGAs, GPUs, and new processor designs ● Non-Volatile Main Memories ● POSIX Issues and Object Stores ● Emerging AI/DL Workloads ● Interoperability with “cold” data ● Understandability and machine introspection for storage and I/O 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-Volatile Main Memories in the I/O Stack ● Memory style addressing of persistent storage ● Ad-hoc File Systems ● Middleware to provide Quality-of-Service and ML-Interfaces ● Automatic Data Placement ● In-storage processing and serverless computing ● Highly distributed storage resources (at the Edge, Fog, and HPC/Cloud) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-Volatile Memories in I/O Stack & Deep I/O Hierarchies ● Data-centric Computing ● Object Storage and Cloud Convergence ● Feature Rich APIs ● Quality-of-Service and Understandability ● Data Management ● Adaption for new Programming Paradigms and Workloads ● Adaptions for new Hardware: Processing Environments & Interconnection Networks

Figure 1: Overview of technical I/O and storage research priorities in previous SRAs^{1,2,3}.

¹ ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda for High-Performance Computing in Europe 3 (SRA 3), 2017. Available online: https://etp4hpc.eu/download/60/sra/4319/etp4hpc_sra-3_2017.pdf

ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda for High-Performance Computing in Europe 4 (SRA 4), 2020. Available online: https://etp4hpc.eu/download/60/sra/4320/etp4hpc_sra-4_2020.pdf

ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda for High-Performance Computing in Europe 5 (SRA 5), 2022. Available online: https://etp4hpc.eu/download/60/sra/4321/etp4hpc_sra-5_2022.pdf

State-of-the-Art

The landscape of I/O and storage systems in HPC has evolved significantly in recent years, driven by the increasing demands of data-intensive workloads and the rapid advancement of storage technologies. Historically, storage systems relied primarily on two media types: spinning disks (HDDs) and tapes. Often employed together in Hierarchical Storage Management (HSM) configurations, disks provided high I/O throughput while tapes offered long-term storage capacity. The advent of SSDs has significantly increased storage performance, further enhanced by the NVMe bus. This has led to a more complex storage hierarchy, incorporating various SSD types (or even NVRAM), HDDs, and tapes. In the following, a brief overview of key trends, developments, and technologies in HPC I/O and storage is discussed.

I/O and Storage Technologies

HPC environments require advanced storage systems that balance performance, capacity, cost, and energy efficiency to support the vast volumes of data generated by simulations, scientific experiments, and large-scale computations. Several storage technologies and architectures have emerged to address the growing demands of modern HPC workloads, each offering distinct advantages based on these trade-offs. Additionally, the emergence of new interconnect technologies for storage and memory is enhancing the overall performance and efficiency of HPC systems. Figure 2 provides an overview of the increasing complexity of storage architectures in HPC systems, both in terms of software and hardware technologies.

Figure 2: Heterogeneity of hardware and software of storage architectures in HPC systems.

The HPC parallel I/O stack⁴ is a multi-layered system designed to support I/O workloads from serial or parallel scientific applications. This stack consists of high-level I/O libraries, middleware I/O libraries, optimization layers, and parallel file systems (PFS), all of which bridge applications and storage hardware. As data passes through these layers, access

patterns are reshaped by various abstractions and optimization techniques, such as scheduling, aggregation, and compression. However, some context is lost along the way, with the file system often unaware of the source or transformations applied to I/O requests.

⁴ Jean Luca Bez, Suren Byna, and Shadi Ibrahim. 2023. I/O Access Patterns in HPC Applications: A 360-Degree Survey. ACM Comput. Surv. 56, 2, Article 46 (February 2024), 41 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3611007>

High-level I/O libraries, like HDF5⁵, NetCDF⁶ / PnetCDF⁷, and ADIOS⁸, offer data models and abstractions to manage files efficiently, allowing for data portability and high performance. Some domain-specific libraries, such as ROOT⁹ (for high-energy physics) and FITS¹⁰ (for astronomy), cater to specialized needs. Additionally, applications may use MPI-IO¹¹, POSIX I/O¹², or STDIO for direct file system access. MPI-IO, with its higher-level data abstraction, allows for complex parallel I/O patterns and optimization opportunities, while POSIX I/O provides byte-level access but lacks inherent support for parallelism. STDIO focuses on streams of bytes and is often used in genomics, though it lacks random access capabilities.

I/O forwarding¹³, originally developed for Blue Gene systems, creates an additional layer between compute nodes and PFS servers, reducing concurrent node access to storage servers and enabling optimizations. This layer

forwards I/O requests from applications to the PFS, where they can be better managed.

In large-scale HPC systems, the PFS provides shared, persistent storage with a global namespace across distributed storage servers. The PFS includes both data and metadata servers, with the latter managing file information, such as sizes and permissions. Popular PFS implementations like Lustre¹⁴, IBM Spectrum Scale (previously known as GPFS)¹⁵, and BeeGFS¹⁶ use techniques like *data striping*¹⁷ to distribute file data across multiple storage nodes for enhanced performance. These file systems offer logical abstractions over various storage devices, such as Hard Disk Drives (HDDs), Solid-State Drives (SSDs), or Redundant Array of Independent Drives (RAID) arrays, enabling efficient and scalable data management in HPC environments. In recent

⁵ The HDF Group. 2022. Hierarchical Data Format, Version 5. The HDF Group. <https://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>

⁶ Choonghwan Lee, MuQun Yang, and Ruth Aydt. 2008. NetCDF-4 Performance Report. HDF Group (THG). https://www.hdfgroup.org/pubs/papers/2008-06_netcdf4_perf_report.pdf

⁷ J. Li, WK Liao, A. Choudhary, R. Ross, R. Thakur, W. Gropp, R. Latham, A. Siegel, B. Gallagher, and M. Zingale. 2003. Parallel NetCDF: A high-performance scientific I/O interface. In Proceedings of the 2003 ACM/IEEE Conference on Supercomputing (SC'03). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1048935.1050189>

⁸ Liu, Q., Logan, J., Tian, Y., Abbasi, H., Podhorszki, N., Choi, J.Y., Klasky, S., Tchoua, R., Lofstead, J., Oldfield, R., Parashar, M., Samatova, N., Schwan, K., Shoshani, A., Wolf, M., Wu, K. and Yu, W. (2014), Hello ADIOS: the challenges and lessons of developing leadership class I/O frameworks. *Concurrency Computat.: Pract. Exper.*, 26: 1453-1473. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.3125>

⁹ Antcheva, I., Ballintijn, M., Bellenot, B., Biskup, M., Brun, R., Buncic, N., Canal, P., Casadei, D., Couet, O., Fine, V. and Franco, L., 2009. ROOT—A C++ framework for petabyte data storage, statistical analysis and visualization. *Computer Physics Communications*, 180(12), pp.2499-2512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2009.08.005>

¹⁰ R. J. Hanisch, A. Farris, E. W. Greisen, W. D. Pence, B. M. Schlesinger, P. J. Teuben, R. W. Thompson, and A. Warnock. 2001. Definition of the Flexible Image Transport System (FITS)*. *Astronomy & Astrophysics* 376, 1 (2001), 359–380. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20010923>

¹¹ Peter Corbett, Dror Feitelson, Sam Fineberg, Yarsun Hsu, Bill Nitzberg, Jean-Pierre Prost, Marc Snir, Bernard Traversat, and Parkson Wong. 1995. Overview of the MPI-IO parallel I/O interface. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on I/O in Parallel and Distributed Systems (IPPS'95). 1–15.

¹² International Organization for Standardization. 1996. Information Technology—Portable Operating System Interface (POSIX). IEEE, Los Alamitos, CA.

¹³ Almási, G. et al. (2003). An Overview of the Blue Gene/L System Software Organization. In: Kosch, H., Böszörményi, L., Hellwagner, H. (eds) Euro-Par 2003 Parallel Processing. Euro-Par 2003. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 2790. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-45209-6_79

¹⁴ Anjus George, Rick Mohr, James Simmons, and Sarp Oral. 2021. Understanding Lustre Internals (2nd Ed.). Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1824954>

¹⁵ Frank Schmuck and Roger Haskin. 2002. GPFS: A shared-disk file system for large computing clusters. In Proceedings of the 1st USENIX Conference on File and Storage Technologies (FAST'02). 19–es.

¹⁶ Frank Herold and Sven Breuner. 2018. An Introduction to BeeGFS. Technical Report. ThinkParQ. https://www.beegfs.io/docs/whitepapers/Introduction_to_BeeGFS_by_ThinkParQ.pdf

¹⁷ Jan Stender, Björn Kolbeck, Felix Hupfeld, Eugenio Cesario, Erich Focht, Matthias Hess, Jesús Malo, and Jonathan Martí. 2008. Striping without sacrifices: Maintaining POSIX semantics in a parallel file system. In Proceedings of the 1st USENIX Workshop on Large-Scale Computing (LASCO'08).

years, Object Storage^{18,19,20} has gained traction in HPC due to its scalability, flexibility, and cost-effectiveness. Unlike traditional hierarchical file systems, object storage stores data as discrete objects with unique identifiers and metadata, allowing for greater scalability. Systems such as DAOS²¹, Ceph/RADOS²², and MinIO²³ enable HPC applications to store massive amounts of data across distributed storage nodes, offering high durability through replication and erasure coding. Object storage is particularly useful in environments where scalability and flexibility are crucial, though it is not as optimized for low-latency access as PFS. Furthermore, cloud storage and data lakes are increasingly integrated into HPC systems to manage large volumes of raw data. Cloud platforms like AWS S3, Google Cloud Storage, and Azure Blob Storage offer virtually unlimited storage capacity with pay-as-you-go models, making them attractive for managing fluctuating workloads and long-term data retention. Data lakes, often implemented in hybrid HPC-cloud ecosystems, facilitate the storage of diverse datasets, enabling advanced analytics, machine learning, and AI-driven discovery processes.

Flash storage, typically in the form of SSDs, provides the best performance among storage options, excelling in both read and write throughput with lower latency than traditional storage mediums. However, its higher cost per gigabyte makes it less economical for extensive deployments. Flash storage is ideal for

workloads requiring fast data access, such as real-time simulations or large-scale analytics, where minimizing I/O bottlenecks is critical. Due to its cost, flash is frequently selectively deployed within HPC architectures, commonly in burst buffers or caching layers to enhance performance where needed most. HDDs, while slower, remain a staple in HPC due to their lower cost per terabyte. Though they offer less impressive performance, particularly for random I/O, they provide ample capacity for storing large datasets. HDDs are typically used for long-term or less frequently accessed data, where capacity and cost-effectiveness are prioritized over speed. Magnetic tapes offer the lowest cost per terabyte but with significantly higher access latency, making them ideal for archival storage. Despite the slower access times, magnetic tapes remain popular for storing large datasets that are rarely accessed but must be retained for future analysis or compliance purposes.

In recent years, burst buffers²⁴, often based on Non-Volatile Memory Express (NVMe) SSDs²⁵, have become a critical component in modern HPC storage architectures. These high-

¹⁸ J. Liu et al., "Evaluation of HPC Application I/O on Object Storage Systems," 2018 IEEE/ACM 3rd International Workshop on Parallel Data Storage & Data Intensive Scalable Computing Systems (PDSW-DISCS), Dallas, TX, USA, 2018, pp. 24-34, doi: 10.1109/PDSW-DISCS.2018.00005.

¹⁹ Gadban, F.; Kunkel, J. Analyzing the Performance of the S3 Object Storage API for HPC Workloads. *Appl. Sci.* 2021, 11, 8540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11188540>

²⁰ Lackschewitz, N.M., Krey, S., Nolte, H., Christgau, S., Oeste, S. and Kunkel, J., 2022. Performance Evaluation of Object Storages (NHR2022). https://gwdg.de/pdf/Performance_Evaluation_of_Object_Storages_NHR2022_.pdf

²¹ Hennecke, M. et al. (2023). DAOS Beyond Persistent Memory: Architecture and Initial Performance Results. In: Bienz, A., Weiland, M., Baboulin, M., Kruse, C. (eds) High Performance Computing. ISC High Performance 2023. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-40843-4_26

²² Feiyi Wang, Mark Nelson, Sarp Oral, Scott Atchley, Sage Weil, Bradley W. Settlemyer, Blake Caldwell, and Jason Hill. 2013. Performance and scalability evaluation of the Ceph parallel file system. In Proceedings of the 8th Parallel Data Storage Workshop (PDSW '13). <https://doi.org/10.1145/2538542.2538562>

²³ MinIO Object Storage for Linux: <https://min.io/docs/minio/linux/>

²⁴ N. Liu et al., "On the role of burst buffers in leadership-class storage systems," 2012 IEEE 28th Symposium on Mass Storage Systems and Technologies (MSST), 2012, pp. 1-11, doi: 10.1109/MSST.2012.6232369.

²⁵ Li, Q., Wei, D., Gao, W., Xie, X. (2020). NV-BSP: A Burst I/O Storage Pool Based on NVMe SSDs. In: Dong, D., Gong, X., Li, C., Li, D., Wu, J. (eds) Advanced Computer Architecture. ACA 2020. Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 1256. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-8135-9_13

performance storage layers^{26,27} act as temporary caches for data generated during computational jobs, reducing I/O bottlenecks by offering higher throughput and lower latency than traditional storage solutions. Positioned between compute nodes and slower storage systems, burst buffers improve efficiency by speeding up data writes and reads during intense computational phases, thereby reducing the time jobs spend waiting for I/O.

NVMe is revolutionizing HPC storage performance by offering a high-performance, low-latency interface specifically designed for SSDs. Unlike traditional interfaces such as SATA or SAS, NVMe maximizes the speed of flash storage, reducing command overhead and improving data transfer speeds. This makes NVMe ideal for high-frequency, data-intensive HPC workloads. Also, NVMe supports multiple I/O queues, which can be processed in parallel, optimizing data access in systems with numerous compute nodes. InfiniBand, the de-facto standard for high-speed interconnects in HPC, provides much higher bandwidth and lower latency than Ethernet, making it ideal for data transfers between compute nodes and storage systems. Its superior performance reduces communication overhead, improving overall system efficiency. InfiniBand is widely used in HPC clusters where fast data transfers and low-latency access to distributed datasets are essential. Finally, Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) technology enhances HPC efficiency by allowing memory-to-memory data transfers between nodes without involving the operating system. This reduces CPU overhead

and latency, accelerating data transfers. RDMA is especially beneficial for large-scale data movement, such as checkpointing and in-memory data analytics, where minimizing latency is crucial.

Optimization Techniques for Parallel I/O

Efficient I/O optimization is critical to reducing bottlenecks and enhancing the overall performance of HPC applications. Several techniques have been introduced and researched to achieve these optimizations, including the following examples:

- **Data Placement:** Optimizing where data is stored is crucial to minimizing I/O bottlenecks. Techniques such as data locality ensure that data is placed closer to the compute nodes that need it, reducing transfer times. Load balancing^{28,29} helps distribute I/O operations evenly across storage systems, preventing hotspots and ensuring smoother access to data.
- **I/O Libraries:** Libraries like MPI-IO and POSIX I/O provide efficient, standardized interfaces for accessing data from parallel file systems. MPI-IO, for example, allows applications to perform high-level I/O operations across multiple nodes, facilitating optimized, collective access to large datasets^{30,31}, while maintaining compatibility with HPC storage systems like Lustre and GPFS.

²⁶ A. Kougkas, H. Devarajan, X. -H. Sun and J. Lofstead, "Harmonia: An Interference-Aware Dynamic I/O Scheduler for Shared Non-volatile Burst Buffers," 2018 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (CLUSTER), 2018, pp. 290-301, doi: 10.1109/CLUSTER.2018.00046.

²⁷ Vef, MA., Moti, N., Süß, T. et al. GekkoFS — A Temporary Burst Buffer File System for HPC Applications. *J. Comput. Sci. Technol.* 35, 72–91 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11390-020-9797-6>

²⁸ Arnab K. Paul, Sarah Neuwirth, Bharti Wadhwa, Feiyi Wang, Sarp Oral, and Ali R. Butt. 2024. Tarazu: An Adaptive End-to-end I/O Load-balancing Framework for Large-scale Parallel File Systems. *ACM Trans. Storage* 20, 2, Article 11 (May 2024), 42 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3641885>

²⁹ A. Bağbaba, "Improving Collective I/O Performance with Machine Learning Supported Auto-tuning," 2020 *IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium Workshops (IPDPSW)*, New Orleans, LA, USA, 2020, pp. 814-821, doi: 10.1109/IPDPSW50202.2020.00138.

³⁰ Q. Kang et al., "Improving MPI Collective I/O for High Volume Non-Contiguous Requests With Intra-Node Aggregation," in *IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems*, vol. 31, no. 11, pp. 2682-2695, 1 Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPDS.2020.3000458.

³¹ Bouhrour, S., Pepin, T. and Jaeger, J., 2022. Towards leveraging collective performance with the support of MPI 4.0 features in MPC. *Parallel Computing*, 109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parco.2021.102860>

- **Asynchronous I/O:** This technique overlaps I/O operations with computation by allowing I/O tasks to run in the background while the processor continues working. By hiding I/O latency, asynchronous I/O^{32,33} improves overall performance, ensuring that I/O operations do not become a bottleneck in data-intensive applications.
- **Data Compression:** Compressing data^{34,35} before storage reduces the amount of data being read from or written to storage systems, leading to faster I/O operations and lower storage requirements. This is particularly beneficial for applications where large datasets need to be processed or transferred, as it can also reduce network bandwidth usage.

In addition to these techniques, data transfer between geographically distant HPC centres is an important focus. Many centres operate parallel file systems like scratch storage for high I/O performance and home filesystems for longer-term storage, with external access typically through SSH-based protocols (SCP, SFTP, Rsync). Object storage protocols like S3 or Swift, or tools like iRODS and Rucio, can facilitate faster, secure data movement between centres, improving I/O efficiency across distributed HPC environments.

³² Lee, S., Kang, Q., Wang, K., Balewski, J., Sim, A., Agrawal, A., Choudhary, A., Nugent, P., Wu, K. and Liao, W.K., "Asynchronous I/O Strategy for Large-Scale Deep Learning Applications," 2021 IEEE 28th International Conference on High Performance Computing, Data, and Analytics (HiPC), doi: 10.1109/HiPC53243.2021.00046.

³³ H. Tang, Q. Koziol, J. Ravi and S. Byna, "Transparent Asynchronous Parallel I/O Using Background Threads," in IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 891-902, 1 April 2022, doi: 10.1109/TPDS.2021.3090322.

³⁴ H. Tang, S. Byna, N. A. Petersson and D. McCallen, "Tuning Parallel Data Compression and I/O for Large-scale Earthquake Simulation," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data), Orlando, FL, USA, 2021, pp. 2992-2997, doi: 10.1109/BigData52589.2021.9671876.

³⁵ S. Li, P. Lindstrom and J. Clyne, "Lossy Scientific Data Compression With SPERR," 2023 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS), St. Petersburg, FL, USA, 2023, pp. 1007-1017, doi: 10.1109/IPDPS54959.2023.00104.

Emerging Trends and Challenges

Today, systems achieve peak performances exceeding 100 petaflops. In earlier eras, the role of storage systems was straightforward: they were “supersized” and designed to handle the I/O workloads generated by larger systems that utilized them. As a result, little attention was given to optimizing I/O patterns. In most cases, the parallel file system paradigm was sufficient to maintain data consistency across all clients (the compute nodes in the supercomputer), making it needless to worry about storage systems—they could effectively handle nearly any situation. The landscape changes significantly when it comes to Exascale computing, which is not merely about building larger systems with greater compute power. It also represents a major evolution in HPC system architecture and a technological game changer^{36,37}. This shift introduces new challenges, each posing potential obstacles to the current paradigms used in today's storage systems. When examining Exascale, we can identify the following emerging trends.

The challenge of *data scalability* is a familiar issue in HPC: the larger the supercomputer, the greater the storage needs. In the context of Exascale, systems are expected to manage tens or even hundreds of exabytes. While reaching these volumes is feasible—primarily a matter of acquiring enough tapes and robots to handle them—there is a crucial aspect that must not be overlooked: the growth of metadata and the challenges of locating specific data. Indexing exabytes may require databases exceeding

10TB or even 100TB, which need to reference both classical POSIX metadata and user-defined metadata. Without proper management of metadata and indexing methods, finding the exact data needed by an end-user could become a “needle in a haystack” problem. POSIX offers a structured hierarchy of files and directories to organize the data space, but this is no longer sufficient at the extreme scale of today's file systems. As a result, two key trends are emerging. The first is the introduction of external services, such as metadata catalogues, to simplify data management. These services are often embedded within object stores, where data management challenges are particularly pronounced. The second trend involves more sophisticated approaches, such as the use of metadata ontologies tailored to specific scientific domains or the adoption of specialized, holistic file formats like HDF5 or ASDF, which integrate both data and metadata.

Supercomputers capable of achieving exaflop performance will be larger and more powerful than those in current machine rooms, intensifying the need for *system scalability*. From a storage system perspective, this means handling a significantly larger number of client systems. It is reasonable to anticipate managing up to 100,000 clients accessing the storage. At such a massive scale, maintaining consistent data across all clients and end-users becomes increasingly complex. This challenge is closely tied to another: managing a vast number of clients requires large state

³⁶ Philip Carns, Julian Kunkel, Kathryn Mohror, and Martin Schulz. Understanding I/O Behavior in Scientific and Data-Intensive Computing (Dagstuhl Seminar 21332). In Dagstuhl Reports, Volume 11, Issue 7, pp. 16-75, Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik (2021). <https://doi.org/10.4230/DagRep.11.7.16>

³⁷ Daniel Medeiros, Eric B. Gregory, Philippe Couvee, James Hawkes, Sebastien Gougeaud, Maïke Gilliot, Olivier Bressand, Yoann Valeri, Julien Jaeger, Damien Chapon, Frederic Bournaud, Loïc Strafella, Daniel Caviedes-Voullième, Ghazal Tashakor, Jolanta Zjupa, Max Holicki, Tom Ridley, Yanik Müller, Filipe Souza Mendes Guimarães, Wolfgang Frings, Jan-Oliver Mirus, Ilya Zhukov, Eric

Rodrigues Borba, Nafiseh Moti, Reza Salkhordeh, Nadia Derbey, Salim Mimouni, Simon Derr, Buket Benek Gursoy, James Grogan, Radek Furfánek, Martin Golasowski, Kateřina Slaninová, Jan Martinovič, Jan Faltýnek, Jenny Wong, Metin Cakircali, Tiago Quintino, Simon Smart, Olivier Iffrig, Sai Narasimhamurthy, Sonja Happ, Michael Rauh, Stephan Krempel, Mark Wiggins, Jiří Nováček, André Brinkmann, Stefano Markidis, and Philippe Deniel. 2024. IO-SEA: Storage I/O and Data Management for Exascale Architectures. In Proceedings of the 21st ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers: Workshops and Special Sessions (CF '24 Companion). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3637543.3654620>

machines, which in turn demand substantial memory resources to function effectively. Storage system clients may face memory constraints, making it difficult to sustain advanced features like data consistency. Specifically, technical challenges arise in handling parallel accesses, relaxed consistency, and multi-tenancy at such a scale.

A few years ago, Intel introduced the many-core paradigm, leading to the now-discontinued Xeon Phi CPU family. The idea of packing numerous compute cores into a single node was appealing: memory could be shared between cores, significantly reducing communication latency between the compute tasks assigned to each core. Although Xeon Phi is no longer around, the concept has gained new momentum with the rise of GPUs in HPC, marking the beginning of the **CPU/GPU evolution**. GPUs, connected via high-speed buses, offer numerous vectorized compute cores, far surpassing what Xeon Phi initially promised. To maximize the potential of GPUs, “fat nodes”—nodes embedding many chips—are now common. From a user's perspective, particularly from the standpoint of compute code, each task pinned to a compute core requires a specific amount of RAM to function properly. Although this memory requirement is relatively modest by today's standards, ranging from 2GB to 10GB, the availability of multiple GPUs per node means that thousands of tasks can be executed concurrently. While this might not seem problematic, given that available memory has also grown, the unfortunate reality is that memory is not scaling as quickly as the number of cores. The memory-to-core ratio has reversed, creating an imbalance. As a result, compute jobs consume the majority of available memory, leaving less space for the operating system, which must now contend with these constraints. This creates significant challenges for certain mechanisms—such as distributed lock managers—which may struggle to function effectively under these conditions.

The convergence with AI is driving supercomputers toward fat node architectures, where each node houses multiple GPUs interconnected with multiple CPUs, and utilizes a complex memory hierarchy that includes HBM and NUMA memory banks. These fat nodes function as parallel computers in their own right. One immediate effect of this architecture is a reduction in the number of nodes that need to be connected to the storage system. However, it also means that I/O traffic from a single node becomes more complex and less predictable. Additionally, the economics of fat nodes support the use of node-local storage, which requires file systems to effectively leverage this valuable hardware resource. As a side note, architectures like Superpod³⁸ and other fat node systems often employ dedicated networks for storage, separating data movement from compute traffic.

The next emerging trend focuses on **data placement**. Today's storage technologies encompass a wide range of devices, from NVMe-attached drives to HDDs and tapes. Each type has its advantages and drawbacks: NVMe SSDs are fast with very low latencies, but they are small and expensive, while tapes are slow yet offer massive capacity and consume no power when not in use. Combining these technologies can bring the best of both worlds, if managed wisely—this is how HPC has evolved to utilize deep storage stacks, ranging from NVMe to tapes. It is important to recognize that different types of data have different uses and, consequently, different storage needs. For

³⁸Chang, J., Lu, K., Guo, Y. et al. A survey of compute nodes with 100 TFLOPS and beyond for supercomputers. CCF Trans. HPC 6, 243–262 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42514-024-00188-w>

example, consider a checkpoint-restart file and a database. The checkpoint file is written once, as a whole, and will likely never be read again unless the code restarts, while the database will undergo frequent random reads and writes. Given their distinct characteristics, it makes sense to allocate the appropriate storage medium for each, ensuring that the right data is placed at the right tier within the storage stack. This data placement challenge is multifaceted, requiring policies that determine what data should reside where, potential expansions of metadata (including user-defined metadata), and the development of new tools to implement these policies effectively.

Finally, the challenge of *data heterogeneity* arises as a direct consequence of the previously mentioned trends. Exascale computing enables the tackling of a wide range of problems across diverse scientific domains—such as high-energy physics, climatology, weather forecasting, biology, and more. The surge of interest in AI technologies has also introduced a completely new set of use cases. Each of these fields brings its own datasets and unique approaches to processing them, resulting in a variety of I/O patterns.

As a result, future storage systems must be capable of handling these diverse patterns. They will need to be versatile enough to accommodate the demands of each domain while maintaining high performance and efficient energy consumption.

Upcoming Research Challenges (2025 - 2028)

Significant challenges lie ahead for developing Exascale-ready storage systems. Each of these challenges has the potential to be a major obstacle and must be carefully addressed or circumvented. Such challenges are unprecedented in the history of HPC, necessitating innovative approaches and new paradigms for working with storage systems. This section aims to outline and identify approaches and provide guidance on how to implement them effectively.

Table 1 illustrates the correlation between upcoming research challenges and emerging trends, highlighting that many of the

improvements in storage systems are primarily driven by software advancements. However, this focus introduces a notable bias, as actual performance gains are largely dependent on the steady evolution of hardware components, such as PCI generations, Flash technologies, and network bandwidth. A key issue arises: how can the European Union community assume the continuous advancement of hardware while placing disproportionate emphasis on software-driven solutions? This imbalance underscores the need for a greater recognition of hardware's essential role in driving performance improvements.

Table 1: Correlation between research challenges and emerging trends.

Mean of Achievement	Emerging Trends and Challenges				
	Data Scalability	System Scalability	Compute Architecture	Data Heterogeneity	Interoperability
Middleware integration			Abstraction of the computing substrate	Copes with data diversity / format	Transparent for workflows
Computational storage		Storage as an accelerator increases overall system efficiency			
Data Transfer / Storage Disaggregation					Collaborative supercomputing sites
Multi-tier Systems	Smart data life cycle management	Using both high performance and high capacity media	Brings the data close to the compute code	Smart data placement policies	
Object Store	Flat data in place of hierarchical data organization				
Security against cyber threats					Interoperable systems means open systems, thus security is mandatory
Workflows and fairness		QoS and fair management is a prerequisite			

I/O Subsystem and Middleware Integration

Addressing upcoming challenges for I/O and storage middleware integration in HPC is crucial to ensure that systems can efficiently handle the growing volume and complexity of data, avoid performance bottlenecks, and integrate new technologies without disrupting existing workflows. Tackling these issues is essential for maintaining system reliability, achieving high performance, and optimizing energy efficiency, all of which are critical for enabling future scientific breakthroughs and large-scale computational tasks in areas like AI, climate modeling, and genomics. Specifically, the following challenges for middleware integration can be identified:

- **Data Scalability:** As HPC systems scale, the volume of data generated by applications is growing exponentially, creating challenges for I/O systems to manage this massive influx. Traditional parallel file systems like Lustre or GPFS may struggle to keep up with the sheer data throughput and storage demands. The challenge will lie in developing scalable storage architectures that can efficiently handle both data-intensive workloads and the increasing diversity of applications.
- **Performance Bottlenecks:** Optimizing data transfer between various storage layers—such as memory, SSDs, burst buffers, and disk-based systems—is essential for maintaining high performance. A key challenge will be ensuring that data movement across these layers doesn't create bottlenecks that slow down application performance. Efficient I/O middleware must intelligently manage data placement and retrieval, while minimizing latency and maximizing throughput.
- **Integration of Emerging Technologies:** New storage technologies, like non-volatile memory (NVM), node-local storage, and burst buffers, are being introduced to address performance gaps, but integrating these technologies into existing systems is complex. HPC environments will have to balance the benefits of new hardware with

the legacy infrastructure to ensure compatibility and smooth operation without compromising reliability or performance.

- **Fault Tolerance and Reliability:** As systems scale, failures become more common due to the larger number of components, increasing the need for robust fault tolerance mechanisms in storage systems. Ensuring data integrity and quick recovery from system failures is vital. The challenge will be to design storage middleware that can detect and handle failures efficiently without impacting performance or causing data loss.
- **Energy Efficiency:** HPC systems are energy-intensive, and I/O operations contribute significantly to overall power consumption. With growing environmental concerns and the need for cost-effective systems, reducing the energy footprint of storage operations is a key challenge. This will involve designing middleware that optimizes I/O operations for energy efficiency without sacrificing performance, such as by leveraging energy-aware data placement strategies or reducing unnecessary data movements.

Overcoming these challenges will require a multi-faceted approach that includes the evolution of software, hardware, and architecture to ensure that HPC systems can meet the increasing demands of future workloads.

Computational Storage

Computational Storage introduces an advanced paradigm closely aligned with Edge Computing. By enabling storage devices to process data directly, this approach enhances various performance metrics. Energy efficiency is particularly crucial, given the high costs associated with data movement—10,000

cycles and 100-1,000 nanojoules per byte³⁹. Data movement also leads to issues such as cache pollution and network overheads. Computational Storage is an evolution of active disks^{40,41}, now augmented with Data Processing Units (DPUs). However, as with other scenarios involving multiple execution environments (e.g., multicore systems, clusters, serverless architectures, edge computing), effective orchestration is vital. Middleware must adapt task-based programming paradigms to dynamically allocate workloads between GPUs and CPUs within this new paradigm. Additionally, system-level orchestration mechanisms are essential to prevent the saturation of computational storage resources and networks, and to determine whether to move data or execute processing within the storage itself. Therefore, expanding middleware capabilities and enhancing job schedulers are necessary steps to support this evolution.

When dealing with Exabyte-scale data, simple aggregation techniques can significantly reduce data movement from 1 EB to the order of megabytes (depending on the size of each individual unit). This reduction minimizes network and CPU costs associated with computing values and transferring data. However, several challenges must be addressed in defining data structures for shared devices. The content needs to be comprehensible to all layers and algorithms, and the device must establish clear boundaries between different data sets stored. Additionally, lock management becomes crucial, as multiple software layers (e.g., user applications and storage devices) may concurrently access the same data.

Computational storage offers significant advantages for AI workloads, particularly those that require compiling input-output pairs for machine learning training. Ideally, these pairs are presented to the learning algorithm in

random order. Current storage systems often require loading entire raw datasets, which contain numerous features, even though only a subset is used for the training pairs. This process necessitates costly data pre-processing, reduces flexibility in exploring different feature combinations, and increases storage costs due to dataset duplication. Computational storage can address these issues by avoiding data duplication and enhancing flexibility for ML/AI researchers. Depending on the processing power and model sizes computational storage may also support inference tasks or in federated model training.

Data Transfers and Storage Disaggregation

Cross-compute Centres Data Transfers: The landscape of data transfer protocols across HPC centres is inconsistent, with the most common protocols still relying on SSH. These may not be as efficient as more direct parallel TCP/UDP approaches, particularly with the rise of AI workloads that require training on petabyte-scale datasets. While high-throughput protocols are crucial, challenges also arise from suboptimal network traffic routing through national research networks to the common GEANT network in Europe. Addressing these issues often necessitates collaboration among networking engineers, HPC specialists, and management across different countries.

To improve cross-centre data transfers, we recommend a coordinated effort to conduct basic network throughput benchmarks between centres, ensuring that networking engineers are present for accurate execution. The results will help evaluate existing networking paths across Europe and identify opportunities for optimization. Numerous transfer protocols already utilize parallel network streams to enhance performance, such as multipart transfers via S3⁴² or parallel

³⁹ Curry, Matthew L et al. "Power Use of Disk Subsystems in Supercomputers." (2011)

⁴⁰ Acharya, Anurag, Mustafa Uysal, and Joel Saltz. "Active disks: Programming model, algorithms and evaluation." ACM SIGPLAN Notices 1 Oct. 1998: 81-91.

⁴¹ Riedel, Erik et al. "Active disks for large-scale data processing." Computer 34.6 (2001): 68-74.

⁴² Amazon S3 Service documentation: <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/s3/>

TCP streams with iRODS⁴³. However, these protocols must be evaluated not only for performance but also from operational and user perspectives. Implementations should integrate with local user management systems (like LDAP) to enforce access rights and be compatible with local storage solutions. Additionally, user accessibility is vital, requiring intuitive command-line interfaces (CLI) and web-based graphical user interfaces (GUIs) for monitoring transfers. Easy installation of these tools on users' local computers is essential for facilitating data transfers between users and HPC centres.

Promising methods for transferring public or shared datasets could involve peer-to-peer protocols like BitTorrent, commonly used for distributing operating system updates and HPC cluster boot images. These mature protocols offer robust desktop clients and backend services and should be evaluated for their efficiency in handling large data transfers.

User Access to Data Transfers: Data transfer between users and HPC centres suffers from usability issues. While cloud solutions like Dropbox⁴⁴, OneDrive⁴⁵ and Google Drive⁴⁶ offer streamlined GUIs and user-friendly clients, many open-source alternatives like Owncloud⁴⁷ and Nextcloud⁴⁸ are also available. However, these solutions are often viewed as "centralized," obscuring the actual geographical location of the data. This contradicts the distributed nature of HPC centres, leading users to revert to SSH-based tools, such as parallel rsync⁴⁹ instances managed through custom Bash scripts or GUIs like WinSCP⁵⁰ and Midnight Commander⁵¹.

To enhance usability, it is essential to adapt the streamlined features of cloud-based tools for the HPC environment. This includes implementing transfer protocols capable of handling large data volumes (terabytes) while offering functionalities like link-based sharing

and transfer pausing, similar to those provided by current cloud solutions.

Staging and Automated Data Management: Streamlining available data transfer protocols is just one aspect of a broader initiative aimed at enabling open science through reproducibility and FAIR data sets. To enhance data management services at HPC sites, capabilities for remote triggering of data transfers between HPC clusters, local data storage (projects), and external sites, such as other HPC centres or public data repositories, should be integrated. This process is commonly referred to as data staging. Remote triggering is essential for efficiently managing large data transfers, allowing data to move directly between centres using appropriate transfer protocols, rather than flowing through user workstations. However, determining which data should be transferred and the most effective method for doing so poses significant challenges.

Metadata Catalog: Data in HPC centres are predominantly managed as a structure of POSIX directories and files, with some instances utilizing S3 objects. In contrast, there is a wide array of research data management (RDM) software, such as Invenio and DSpace, which link data to its metadata and serve as destinations for resolving unique identifiers like PIDs and DOIs. While instances of these solutions are currently deployed as public services (e.g., Zenodo, B2SHARE), it remains unclear how to reference datasets stored in HPC centres to maintain data locality for further processing and computation.

Initiatives like EUDAT B2SAFE are noteworthy efforts in the realm of data management, as they facilitate the tracking of data replicas across various locations, including the metadata associated with each data object. Unifying these solutions across different sites will enable automated data staging, utilizing unique IDs such as PIDs or DOIs as references

⁴³ iRODS - Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System <https://irods.org/>

⁴⁴ Dropbox - <https://www.dropbox.com/>

⁴⁵ Microsoft OneDrive: <https://www.microsoft.com/cs-cz/microsoft-365/onedrive/online-cloud-storage>

⁴⁶ Google Drive: https://www.google.com/intl/en_US/drive/

⁴⁷ Owncloud: <https://owncloud.com/>

⁴⁸ Nextcloud: <https://nextcloud.com/>

⁴⁹ Rsync documentation: <https://rsync.samba.org/>

⁵⁰ WinSCP SSH client: <https://winscp.net/eng/index.php>

⁵¹ Midnight Commander file manager: <https://midnight-commander.org/>

previously queried from a metadata catalogue. This unification will also support the development of advanced services, such as metadata notifications, which can alert users or external systems when a new dataset is created, or an existing one is modified.

Data and Storage Management in Multi-Tier Systems

Combining multiple storage technologies within a single system (called multi-tier or hierarchical storage management, HSM) allows for designing systems that are both high-performance and high-capacity at a reduced cost. Thus, this solution is particularly well-suited for designing storage systems for HPC⁵².

Figure 3: Multi-tier storage management.

Data Heterogeneity and Data placement in Multi-tier Systems: To maximize the efficiency of multi-tier systems, strategic data placement is essential. Poor placement, such as storing frequently accessed data on slow media, can significantly degrade system performance. Conversely, keeping outdated data on high-performance storage like SSDs wastes valuable resources. Effective data placement also addresses data heterogeneity by aligning specific data types with their optimal storage media and access paths, based on performance requirements, size, and access frequency. Additionally, optimizing data placement can reduce energy consumption by offloading dormant data to less energy-intensive options, such as magnetic tapes. Several mechanisms can be employed for effective data placement in multi-tier systems:

1. **Static Rule-Based Policies:** These policies are determined by system administrators based on file attributes like access date and size.
2. **Application or User-Guided Policies:** Users or applications provide hints about intended access types and data lifecycle.
3. **Self-Learned Policies:** These policies adapt based on system learning from user habits and access patterns.

Implementing static rule-based policies involves developing policy engines that incorporate configurable rules based on various file attributes, including user-defined ones. However, scaling these to manage policies for billions of files, as seen in the IO-SEA project⁵³ with the open-source Policy Engine RobinHood4^{54,55}, will present significant challenges. User-guided policies align closely with specific needs, allowing users to express

⁵² Thomas Leibovici, "Hierarchical Storage from NVMe to Tapes", EMOSS '22, 2022.

⁵³ <https://iosea-project.eu>

⁵⁴ <https://github.com/robinhood-suite>

⁵⁵ Thomas Leibovici, "Taking back control of HPC file systems with Robinhood Policy Engine", International Workshop on the Lustre Ecosystem: Challenges and Opportunities, March 2015, Annapolis, US.

performance, volume, and data usage duration through APIs or I/O middleware like DASI⁵⁶. Defining effective placement policies requires analysing input/output behaviour, which can be complicated by unpredictable data usage and interactions with other concurrent processes. Machine learning and AI can enhance this process by automating the refinement of placement policies based on observations from past computations. This approach⁵⁷ is promising as it would allow for a more comprehensive consideration of factors affecting data access while alleviating the burden on administrators and developers to manually specify policies.

Data Preservation in Multi-tier Systems:

Another challenge in multi-tier systems is long-term data preservation. As data is moved between storage tiers and undergoes media refreshes, it can be susceptible to corruption from network errors or read/write failures. Additionally, silent corruption may occur when data is "at rest."⁵⁸ To ensure end-to-end data integrity from writing to reuse, it is essential to implement control mechanisms and self-correction features. Early detection of data corruption enhances the chances of recovering lost data from valid copies or regenerating it from accessible datasets. We recommend equipping multi-tier storage systems with mechanisms to maintain data consistency over the long term and enable early corruption detection. This can be accomplished by incorporating check-summing at each data transfer and access step. Utilizing technologies like T10 Data Integrity Field⁵⁹ (T10-DIF) and its evolution, T10 Protection Information⁶⁰ (T10-PI), can facilitate the integration of these

features into storage media standards, allowing for regular self-verification of disk content.

Machine Learning Training: Large scale machine learning training, particularly approaches such as Large Language Models, have specific I/O usage patterns/requirements, characterized by large amounts of read-only data, high bandwidth requirements, and locality benefits. Bespoke multi-tier I/O middleware, handling loading of training data sets onto node-local storage devices, and periodic shuffling of datasets between nodes, has been crucial for large scale LLM training for the leading providers of these models. However, there is currently no mature open source/robust/multipurpose version of this middleware that can easily be used by anyone to replicate these approaches. Developing and researching the I/O middleware approaches that can automatically stage and reorganize read-only data like this, in harmony with application workflows, building on data scheduling approaches such as NORNS⁶¹ or the NEXTGenIO data scheduler⁶². It has the potential to help a wide range of such applications and approaches across disparate computing systems.

⁵⁶ O. Iffrig, J. Hawkes, S. Smart and T. Quintino, "Decoupling data collocation and storage performance using scientifically meaningful object identifiers", HPC I/O in the Data Center Workshop (HPCIODC 2022), 2022.

⁵⁷ Luis Thomas, Sebastien Gougeaud, Stéphane Rubini, Stéphane Rubini, Jalil Boukhobza, "Predicting file lifetimes for data placement in multi-tiered storage systems for HPC", CHEOPS '21.

⁵⁸ D. Fiala, F. Mueller, C. Engelmann, K. Ferreira, R. Brightwell, and R. Riesen, "Detection and correction of silent data corruption for large-scale high-performance computing," North Carolina State University, Tech. Rep. TR 2012-5, May 2012.

⁵⁹ Keith Holt, "End-to-End Data Protection Justification", T10 Technical Committee document 03-224r0, July 2003.

⁶⁰ Seagate, "Safeguarding Data From Corruption", Technology Paper., 2011.

⁶¹ A. Miranda, A. Jackson, T. Tocci, I. Panourgias and R. Nou, "NORNS: Extending Slurm to Support Data-Driven Workflows through Asynchronous Data Staging," 2019 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (CLUSTER), Albuquerque, NM, USA, 2019, pp. 1-12, doi: 10.1109/CLUSTER.2019.8891014.

⁶² Next Generation I/O for Exascale, D5.4 Final report on energy-aware and data-aware scheduling. <https://doi.org/10.3030/671591>

Object Stores and Storage Services

De facto object storage access standards are appearing, such as S3, and are strongly connected to Cloud technologies. They are easy to implement, but could be a potential blocker in the future as they rely on non-optimized protocols (like HTTP or TCP). Research is required into how best to exploit object storage approaches for computational simulation and machine learning applications in a high-performance computing context, and what benefits object storage technologies may provide. Moving from bulk synchronous I/O required to get high performance for parallel file systems to smaller and finer grained I/O operations could change functionality for applications. Meanwhile, it is not yet clear what the common usage patterns that will benefit from this approach are, or what new functionality this new storage paradigm can enable.

With the research and development to understand where object storage approaches best fit in the high performance storage stack, what applications are most likely to benefit from them, and how to best map application I/O to object storage systems, these approaches are likely to become an important high performance part of the next generation of storage approaches providing the very highest performance for Exascale I/O which enabling new methods of performing data storage for applications.

Cybersecurity Strategies for Securing Storage Systems

As European computing centres become increasingly interconnected and open—through integration with identity and service federations—they also face heightened vulnerability to cyberattacks. The immense computing power of these large facilities makes them attractive targets for cryptocurrency

mining and potential tools for leading DDoS attacks or exploiting weaknesses in blockchain algorithms⁶³. Recent years have seen several reported attacks on data centres in Europe. The consequences of a data perspective can be severe: theft of confidential information, data locking by ransomware (crypto-locking)⁶⁴, data destruction, and the release of sensitive information. To mitigate these risks, it is essential to strengthen the security of storage systems. However, to prevent security measures from becoming a burden on users, it is equally important to ensure that the systems remain user-friendly, and that security mechanisms are as interoperable as possible.

Integration of authentication mechanisms will be crucial for data protection, as it ensures that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data. This requires implementing robust, state-of-the-art authentication technologies, such as Kerberos, OpenID Connect, SAML, and FIDO2. However, simply having an authentication mechanism in place is not sufficient; storage systems must effectively integrate and utilize these mechanisms to control data access. We advocate that the development of storage systems will need to focus on the integration of robust authentication mechanisms that comply with the latest recommendations from security experts.

Efficient encryption is another critical component of data protection. When combined with a robust authentication system, encryption safeguards the confidentiality of sensitive data and protects data integrity by preventing unauthorized modifications. Moreover, encryption-based digital signatures confirm the origin of data, thereby enhancing trust in data exchanges among community members. Encryption concerns several aspects of storage:

1. *Encryption of data in transit*: Ensures that data is not intercepted or modified by third

⁶³ Shubhani Aggarwal, Neeraj Kumar, "Attacks on blockchain" in *Advances in Computers*, Volume 121, 2021.

⁶⁴ A. Farion-Melnyk, V. Rozheliuk, T. Slipchenko, S. Banakh, M. Farion and O. Bilan, "Ransomware Attacks: Risks, Protection and Prevention Measures," 2021 11th International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies (ACIT), Deggendorf, Germany, 2021.

parties while being transmitted over networks, especially the internet.

2. *Encryption of stored data*: Prevents data centre operators from accessing users' data and protects against storage media theft.
3. *Encryption of metadata* (file and directory names): These can also contain confidential information.
4. *Fine grain encryption*, for access control of metadata the coarse grain approach based on tenants or subtenants is not sufficient. Depending on the level of clearance of each user or group of users, part of the metadata should be made visible or accessible.

Addressing these various aspects will necessitate significant changes to storage systems, which may impact their performance⁶⁵. Therefore, in addition to developing end-to-end encryption mechanisms (from the user to the storage media), it will be crucial to carefully consider the performance of these mechanisms, particularly within the context of High-Performance Computing applications.

Interplay between HPC File systems and Cloud Storage:

Traditionally, HPC file systems and cloud storage systems use different authentication systems, which limits interoperability and complicates their combined use. Network file systems (such as NFS and Lustre⁶⁶) support Kerberos authentication, allowing users authenticated on a Kerberized computing center to securely access these file systems without re-entering their password. However, accessing a cloud storage system like S3 requires a different authentication mechanism, such as Keystone, necessitating a new password. This discrepancy in authentication methods hinders the implementation of Single Sign-On (SSO) between cloud storage and HPC systems, creating technical barriers and complicating the user experience. To address this issue, it will be essential to develop common authentication mechanisms for both HPC file systems and

cloud storage systems, enabling the implementation of SSO across all platforms.

Protection Against Ransomware: Ransomware is a type of malicious software designed to block access to a computer system or data until a ransom is paid. It typically encrypts the victim's files, making them inaccessible, and demands payment for the decryption key. In recent years, many public institutions and private companies have fallen victim to ransomware attacks. The consequences can include data theft or loss, prolonged service interruptions, significant financial costs (both from service downtime and ransom payments), and damage to the organization's reputation. Therefore, it is crucial to implement effective mechanisms to protect storage systems from this threat.

The most effective defence against ransomware is to regularly back up data to "offline" storage that is not connected to a computer network. This can be achieved using storage media that are physically disconnected or media that are not continuously connected to systems, such as magnetic tapes. For data that does not require frequent access, magnetic tape is particularly advantageous due to its low total cost of ownership (TCO). In an HPC environment managing hundreds of petabytes of data, large-scale data backup requires high-performance tape storage systems. Additionally, to ensure that backups are viable and enable rapid system recovery, it is essential to maintain a consistent state of the data. This requires storage systems to have features that allow for taking "snapshots" of the data state. Combining snapshot capabilities with efficient backups to offline media could provide protection against ransomware and facilitate a swift return to service in the event of an attack. To ease the implementation of these protections, it will also be beneficial to offer robust solutions for logical media disconnection that do not require physical intervention to take the media offline.

⁶⁵ Luka Daoud, Hingkwon Huen, "Performance Study of Software-based Encrypting Data at Rest", Proceedings of 37th International Conference on Computers and Their Applications, Volume 82, 2022.

⁶⁶ D Bourilkov, P Avery, M Cheng, Y Fu, B Kim, J Palencia, R Budden, K Benninger, J L Rodriguez, J Dilascio, "Secure wide area network access to CMS analysis data using the Lustre filesystem", Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2012.

Versatility and Agility: Security is a field that demands continuous evolution and a high level of agility, particularly in large shared systems. The creation of new tenants should be possible within a short timeframe, with the granularity of a job serving as a natural unit in HPC environments. Tenants and subtenants will need to be created and revoked online without requiring complex system reconfigurations. This process could be integrated with the concept of a machine-actionable data management plan.

Detecting suspicious activities is crucial for enhancing security in computing centres and storage systems, beyond the implemented security features. Effective prevention and detection of attacks hinge on monitoring storage system activity, as intrusions often manifest as unusual activity within storage spaces. Advances in machine learning and AI technologies will provide new opportunities for identifying suspicious behaviour⁶⁷. This field of work focuses on two key aspects: instrumenting storage systems to generate detailed access logs—necessary for certain security certifications—and conducting research to analyse these logs for detecting abnormal or malicious behaviour. The ability to detect suspicious activities is closely tied to ransomware protection, as identifying breaches should trigger data protection mechanisms such as switching data to read-only mode.

Auditability is essential for security systems, enabling thorough examination of security measures, data protection mechanisms, and compliance with standards. Cloud providers currently excel in this area, outpacing HPC sites that often use isolated security approaches. Drawing lessons from the healthcare and finance sectors could enhance auditability in HPC environments. We advocate for a collaborative effort to develop clear guidelines, implement standards, and establish compliance methods to improve auditability in HPC sites.

⁶⁷ Syam Akhil Repalle, Venkata Ratnam Kolluru, "Intrusion Detection System using AI and Machine Learning

Addressing Security: The Meluxina Journey

Luxembourg has established itself as a trusted and secure environment, a vision that extends to its national digital infrastructure. Notably, Luxembourg hosts the world's first digital embassy, the [data embassy of Estonia](#). To realize this vision, LuxProvide, the operator of the EuroHPC system Meluxina, achieved ISO27001 certification. This certification enables Meluxina to support local industry actors by adhering to the highest data security standards. It encompasses various elements, including a security roadmap and regular penetration tests. These tests vary depending on the information provided to the attacker, simulating scenarios involving external actors or insiders with different privilege levels. Specific techniques, known as "leg-up," are used to accelerate the effects of dormant attacks, such as compromising systems awaiting zero-day breaches. Through these efforts, LuxProvide not only earned the ISO27001 certification but also developed a practical approach to security. According to Valentin Plugaru, LuxProvide's CTO, key recommendations include improving patch management systems to ensure up-to-date security across the entire supercomputing environment, managing access carefully as the user base evolves, and implementing a general policy to minimize attack surfaces through whitelisting of services and access. Additionally, attention must be given to the security of external data transfers, as IoT devices make it necessary to scrutinize the security of acquisition devices more rigorously.

Algorithm", International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Vol. 04, Dec 2017.

Enhancing Data Management through Workflow Optimization, Fairness, and Performance Engineering Techniques

A workflow outlines the interaction between processing steps (tasks) using graph representations to enable automated and potentially repeated execution. Various workflow engines exist across different communities, and different levels of abstraction are common. Notably, many workflow engines assume either explicit or implicit access to data dependencies. For emerging storage systems, workflow-awareness presents several opportunities and challenges, including performance optimization, enhanced and automated metadata capture to support data indexing and FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse) data principles⁶⁸, and computational storage where the lines between compute and storage systems are increasingly blurred.

Interoperability presents a significant challenge when integrating storage systems with workflow perspectives due to the varying scope, timeframe, and granularity of workflow definitions used by different stakeholders. Often, these workflows are nested and orchestrated by different tools. To address this, research will need to identify relevant and enduring abstractions both in workflow descriptions and in storage services.

Foundation for Automation of Data Management and Performance Optimization: Workflows offer valuable insights into the data lifecycle, enabling the automation of storage needs at the application level. This includes capturing provenance information and metadata for data management systems, supporting FAIR principles. At a lower level, workflows facilitate automation of performance and system optimizations by integrating I/O behaviour and monitoring perspectives. This integration enhances resource management heuristics for data

placement, staging decisions in tiered deployments, and compute shipping.

To implement such automation systems across diverse HPC environments, unified APIs for data movement, job management, and credentials management are essential. While centres provide similar services, technical differences remain, such as the lack of standardized authentication APIs. Although protocols like OAuth 2.0 and SAML are becoming more common due to multi-factor authentication requirements, implementations vary. Mechanisms like SSH certificate authorities or custom PAM modules are adequate for user-based interactions.

Automation primarily depends on machine-to-machine interactions, typically using long-term tokens or API keys in the industrial Cloud domain. These mechanisms are critical for automated job and data management and will gain importance as more HPC systems become available across Europe. These unification efforts are exemplified by major public procurements such as SIMPL and the EuroHPC Federation Platform.

⁶⁸ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management

and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Post-Exascale Vision

Post-exascale storage hierarchies and I/O infrastructures, as outlined in Figure 4, are evolving to address the unprecedented data management challenges posed by advanced computing systems, incorporating deeper storage hierarchies that will enhance efficiency, capacity, and longevity. Traditional storage technologies, including DRAM, SSDs, and HDDs, will be complemented by innovative solutions like DNA data storage⁶⁹, which offers remarkable density and durability by encoding

data within biological molecules. This emerging layer can potentially store vast amounts of information in minuscule physical volumes, making it ideal for archival purposes. By implementing multi-tiered storage architectures, future HPC systems will be able to dynamically allocate data across these diverse layers, optimizing performance and energy consumption while ensuring long-term data preservation and accessibility in an increasingly data-driven landscape.

Figure 4: New storage technologies and post-exascale vision.

⁶⁹ K. Weide-Zaage, "DNA Digital-Storage: Advantages, Approach and Technical Implementation," 2024 Pan Pacific Strategic Electronics Symposium (Pan Pacific), 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.23919/PanPacific60013.2024.10436508.

Hyperconverged Infrastructures in HPC Centres

Hyperconverged infrastructures (HCI) integrate compute, storage, and networking resources into a single, unified system, simplifying management and scalability. This approach consolidates multiple data centre functions into a single platform, typically managed through a single interface. By combining hardware and software in a streamlined, modular design, HCI enables more efficient resource utilization and easier expansion. As we move beyond exascale computing, the vision for hyperconverged infrastructures in HPC centres focuses on unprecedented integration, efficiency, and flexibility. Post-exascale HCI will seamlessly combine compute, storage, and networking resources into a unified, software-defined environment. This integration will streamline management, reduce latency, and optimize resource utilization, crucial for handling the massive data and complex workloads typical of post-exascale systems.

Future HCI in HPC will leverage advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning to enhance automation and predictive maintenance. AI-driven resource management will dynamically allocate resources based on real-time workload demands, ensuring optimal performance and energy efficiency. Enhanced fault tolerance and self-healing capabilities will minimize downtime and maintain system reliability. The post-exascale era will also see increased adoption of heterogeneous architectures within HCI, incorporating CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and specialized accelerators. This diversity will support a wide range of applications, from scientific simulations to AI research. Standardized, open-source middleware will play a pivotal role in achieving interoperability across these varied components, simplifying integration and scaling. Ultimately, post-exascale hyperconverged infrastructures will empower

⁷⁰ Julian Kunkel. Toward IOVerbs with the Memory-Centric Storage for Exascale (MCSE) Project, HPC-IODC@ISC23. <https://hps.vi4io.org/media/events/2023/iocd23-mcse.pdf>

researchers and organizations to tackle even more complex scientific and engineering challenges, driving innovation and discovery in the next frontier of HPC.

Blurring the Line between Storage Systems and the Network

In the current landscape, I/O operations and storage management often involve pushing bytes across the network, with these components operating independently of each other. This disconnection can lead to bottlenecks, particularly during I/O bursts, which negatively impact performance. Integrating storage systems with network infrastructure could yield significant benefits. For instance, if the network can advertise its available bandwidth on specific links, I/O operations could be adjusted to prevent bottlenecks. Additionally, if the network offers multiple routes with varying performance levels between endpoints, the storage system could prioritize critical operations on the best link while using alternate routes for less critical tasks, such as checkpoint-restart file management. Considerations and research studies in these domains have been initiated in projects such as IO-SEA and RED-SEA (both funded by EuroHPC JU) and must be continued in future collaborations. Another example is the Memory-Centric Storage for Exascale (MCSE) Project^{70,71}, which explores alternative storage APIs. The aim of this project is to eliminate the separation of main and non-volatile memory and to bring them together in a distributed computing system under a standardized interface so that different classes of storage media can be used flexibly in HPC workflows.

Computational Storage

In data centres and across multiple centres, data movement can be minimized by performing computations directly on the data

⁷¹ Sebastian Oeste. Introducing I/O-Verbs a semantic aware API as POSIX alternative, HPC-IODC@ISC24. <https://hps.vi4io.org/media/events/2024/iocd24-oeste.pdf>

and then transferring only the results, rather than downloading raw data copies. Computational storage paradigms enhance storage systems with computational capabilities, but programming these systems efficiently remains an open research question, particularly for large legacy applications. The adoption of workflow- and task-based programming paradigms by domain users, along with emerging industry standards at the storage device level, addresses key challenges in computational storage. Additionally, workflows spanning the entire computing continuum—from edge to cloud and HPC—naturally promote the use of task-based programming models (also for provenance reasons). A missing perspective is the integration of resource management and monitoring systems and metadata to empower performance estimates to drive temporal and spatial scheduling decisions.

Monitoring and Analyzing the Collected Data with AI

As data centre systems have grown larger and more complex since the Terascale era, this trend will intensify with the advent of Exascale computing. Managing these intricate systems has become as daunting as extracting the square root of pi with an abacus. Monitoring has never been more critical: the sheer number of subsystems and elements generates a vast amount of data, with numerous probes and metrics to collect. While individual data collection is straightforward and requires minimal bandwidth, interpreting and correlating the entire dataset is challenging. A promising approach is to aggregate monitoring data in an unstructured format, potentially using NoSQL databases, and analyze it with AI tools⁷². Machine learning and deep learning frameworks, for example, can help identify correlations between different components,

leading to optimizations and early detection of hardware issues and misconfigurations.

Post Exascale KPI: Power Consumption is vital

In storage systems and I/O operations, traditional metrics and KPIs have focused primarily on latencies and bandwidths, both from a point-to-point perspective (data transfer between a single agent and a peer) and a global perspective (overall performance of the storage system). Many RFP documents use these KPIs to size storage systems, often summarizing requirements as “the ability to transfer the entire RAM of the compute system in less than X minutes.”

With the challenges posed by Exascale computing and the development of new paradigms, it is crucial to consider additional KPIs. While not necessarily more or less relevant, these new KPIs will highlight different aspects of the problem, as storage systems become increasingly complex and multifaceted. The rise in power consumption associated with compute centre design, including GPU design and cooling infrastructure, underscores the need to address energy efficiency. Storage systems, being significant energy consumers, will likely continue to utilize tapes due to their lack of power consumption when not in use, emphasizing the importance of HSM. Future designs should focus on keeping I/O operations close to compute nodes and reducing network distance to data nodes, which could lead to significant optimizations and lower energy costs. Exascale systems are evolving towards disaggregated architectures, such as the Modular Supercomputing Architecture (MSA)⁷³, which could further enhance efficiency.

⁷² S. Neuwirth and A. K. Paul, "Parallel I/O Evaluation Techniques and Emerging HPC Workloads: A Perspective," 2021 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (CLUSTER), Portland, OR, USA, 2021, pp. 671-679. <https://doi.org/10.1109/Cluster48925.2021.00100>.

⁷³ Neuwirth, S., 2023. Modular Supercomputing and its Role in Europe's Exascale Computing Strategy. PoS, p.245. <https://doi.org/10.22323/1.430.0245>

Data Gravity

Large amounts of data either remain co-located with data generation sources or are stored in long-term archives. Despite significant global investments in network capacity, the disparity between available bandwidth and the volume of data that needs to be moved makes it increasingly impractical to download entire datasets before analysis. To optimize the use of shared infrastructures and reduce financial and environmental costs, research into workflow and data locality-aware resource orchestration is essential.

This focus can significantly impact both storage system and supercomputer architectures. Data storage incurs costs, even on tapes, which are energy-efficient only when data is accessed, and moving data is also expensive. As supercomputers become more powerful and complex, data movement becomes inevitable. Deep storage hierarchies, ranging from fast NVMe devices to slow but capacious tapes, necessitate data transfers between different storage levels and across servers. Consequently, data centres and computer centres must be designed to minimize distances between components. Both storage systems and applications need to be optimized to reduce data movement. Additionally, networks, which have historically been over-provisioned relative to I/O activity, are now under significant strain. With Exascale systems, the larger data volumes and complex data movements place unprecedented pressure on network infrastructure, making it a critical barrier to achieving Exascale performance.

Key R&I Recommendations

Based on our observations, we identify the following actionable research and innovation recommendations for the upcoming years:

1. Characterizing I/O System Pressure:

Conduct Comprehensive I/O Pattern Studies: Investigate common I/O patterns to characterize the “pressure” on I/O systems. Initiatives like the *I/O Trace Initiative*⁷⁴ from projects like IO-SEA and ADMIRE should be expanded to inform system optimizations.

AI for System Monitoring: Leverage AI and machine learning tools to monitor and analyze I/O and storage system data, providing real-time optimization, fault detection, and predictive maintenance in complex HPC environments.

2. Object Storage and Distributed File Systems:

Develop Bridges between Object Stores and Applications: Invest in tools to seamlessly integrate object stores with HPC applications. This includes building file systems on top of object stores to overcome semantic gaps.

Convergence of HPC and Cloud Object Stores: Align HPC object store usage with cloud technologies, ensuring interoperability of tools and protocols between environments.

3. Data Placement and Energy Efficiency:

Optimize Data Locality and Placement in Multi-Tier Systems: Research smart data placement across storage tiers, from NVMe SSDs to tapes, to minimize data movement and reduce energy consumption. Develop advanced metadata cataloging systems (e.g., EUDAT B2SAFE) to track data and support automated staging between HPC clusters and external

repositories. This will ensure efficient life cycle management.

Energy-Efficient Data Transfer Methods: Focus on reducing energy costs associated with data movement, employing data aggregation techniques to optimize bandwidth usage and reduce power consumption.

4. Fault Tolerance and Data Protection:

Protection Against Hardware Corruption: Develop mechanisms to protect data from hardware failures, such as erasure coding and multiple version management to ensure data redundancy.

Ransomware and Cyberattack Protection: Strengthen storage systems against cyber threats like ransomware, integrating offline backups (e.g., tapes) and snapshot capabilities for rapid recovery.

5. Computational Storage and Edge Computing:

Leverage Computational Storage: Explore computational storage paradigms to process data near where it is stored, reducing data movement costs. This includes optimizing task-based programming, developing middleware and workflow integration, focusing on integration with AI and machine learning workloads for processing efficiency.

6. Enhancing Middleware and Data Transfers:

Middleware Integration and Scalability: Ensure middleware supports scalable architectures, managing data across multiple storage layers (e.g., NVM, SSD, HDD).

Cross-Centre Data Transfers: Improve cross-centre data transfer protocols, including peer-to-peer protocols like BitTorrent for distributed

⁷⁴ Nafiseh Moti, André Brinkmann, Marc-André Vef, Philippe Deniel, Jesus Carretero, Philip Carns, Jean-Thomas Acquaviva, and Reza Salkhordeh. 2023. The I/O Trace Initiative: Building a Collaborative I/O Archive to

Advance HPC. In Proceedings of the SC '23 Workshops of The International Conference on High Performance Computing, Network, Storage, and Analysis (SC-W '23). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3624062.3624192>

datasets, and enhance user interfaces for managing large transfers.

7. Security and Authentication Mechanisms:

Implement Robust Authentication Systems:

Integrate multi-factor authentication (e.g., Kerberos, OpenID Connect) into HPC systems, ensuring secure and user-friendly access control.

End-to-End Encryption: Focus on developing efficient encryption mechanisms for both data in transit and at rest, ensuring metadata security and compliance with modern standards.

8. Workflow Optimization and Data Management:

Integrate Workflows with Storage Systems:

Automate workflow-aware data management that optimizes resource usage across storage tiers. Implement FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) for data lifecycle management.

By focusing on these key areas, the HPC community can address both current challenges and emerging trends, ensuring scalable, efficient, and secure storage systems for the future.

Conclusions

The Exascale paradigm will enable the development of computing systems with power exceeding one exaflop (10^{18} flops). The architecture and overall topology of these systems will need to be adapted to accommodate such immense computational capabilities. From a storage perspective, several challenges have emerged, highlighting potential issues that necessitate the exploration and implementation of new paradigms. Particularly, managing large parallel and distributed file systems can become complex. While some of these concepts originated in the HPC context, others, such as object storage, are also prevalent in cloud technologies.

The convergence of HPC and cloud computing is increasingly logical, as supercomputers involve intricate network architectures that can be roughly compared to large LANs or MANs⁷⁵. Implementing these new paradigms necessitates a deep understanding and acceptance from users, as it introduces new APIs and access methods.

Data management presents a significant challenge, as storing and moving large volumes of data can be time-consuming and energy-intensive. As data becomes increasingly critical, it is essential to safeguard it against corruption from hardware failures and threats from malicious ransomware. To address these issues, dedicated mechanisms need to be developed to ensure data integrity and security.

⁷⁵ Metropolitan Area Network

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